

Mater Misericordiae
University Hospital
 Sisters of Mercy

Eccles Street, Dublin D07 R2WY, Ireland

Tel: +353 1 8032000 Fax: +353 1 8032404 Web: www.mater.ie

Ospidéal Ollscoile
Mater Misericordiae

Siúrachá na Trícaire

Sráid Eccles, Baile Átha Cliath D07 R2WY, Éire

Not for prescription purposes

CONSENT FORM

Reference Number: JULY 2020 **Protocol Number:** JL-COVID-19 version 4 dated 1

Title of Research Study: ANTICIPATE STUDY- Patients attending Mater Misericordiae University Hospital with COVID19 infection: Baseline profile and care outcomes

Name of Sponsor: Dr Lambert MMUH

Patient Name:

Name of Doctor and Telephone Number: Dr Lambert 716 4530

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information leaflet dated 1 JULY 2020 for the above research study and received an explanation of the nature, purpose, duration, and foreseeable effects and risks of the research study and what my involvement will be.
- I have had time to consider whether to take part in this research study. My questions have been answered satisfactorily and I have received a copy of the Patient Information Leaflet.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary (my choice) and that I am free to withdraw at any time without my medical care or legal rights being affected.
- I am willing to allow access to my medical records by representatives of the sponsor, research ethics committee or local or foreign regulatory authorities but understand that strict confidentiality will be maintained. The purpose of this is to check that the research study is being carried out correctly.
- I am willing to allow a member of the research team to contact me to conduct two interviews and to allow access to my medical records to the research team.
- I agree to take part in the above research study.

.....
 Name of Patient (in block letters) Date Signature

.....
 Name of Person taking consent Date Signature
 (If different from doctor/researcher)

.....
 Doctor/Researcher Date Signature

1 copy for patient, 1 copy for researcher, 1 copy to be inserted in hospital notes

Version 3 dated 1/7//2020

'Commitment to Excellence'

Directors: Mr Thomas Lynch (Chairman), Dr Mary Carmel Burke, Ms Mary Day, Mr Rod Ensor, Mr Tony Garry, Ms Michelle Gibbons, Prof Cecily Kelleher, Prof Brendan Kinsley, Dr Mary McMenamin, Prof Padraic MacMathuna, Sr Eugene Nolan, Ms Eilis O'Brien, Mr Kevin O'Malley, Sr Margherita Rock, Mr David O'Kelly

Designated Activity Company, Registered in Ireland No. 351402 Charity No. CHY203 Registered Office: Eccles Street, Dublin 7